

**ORGANIZATIONAL AND LEGAL FORMS OF BUSINESS ACTIVITIES:
THE EXPERIENCE OF UZBEKISTAN AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR ADAPTING
FOREIGN PRACTICES**

Rustamov Zokir

Institute of Macroeconomic and
Regional Studies, leading specialist

Abstract: This article analyzes the economic and legal nature of organizational and legal forms of entrepreneurial activity. In particular, it examines the characteristics of organizational and legal forms used in practice in the Republic of Uzbekistan, such as sole proprietorships, private enterprises, limited liability companies, and joint-stock companies. In addition, the experience of the United States, Germany, Singapore, and South Korea in this area was analyzed, and the possibilities for adapting some of their mechanisms to the national economy were assessed. The analysis shows that the correct choice of organizational and legal form for business entities plays an important role in attracting investment, ensuring financial stability, and improving the efficiency of business operations. On this basis, a number of practical recommendations have been developed for the conditions in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: *entrepreneurship, legal form, limited liability company, sole proprietorship, corporation, international experience, business environment.*

**ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННО-ПРАВОВЫЕ ФОРМЫ
ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ: ОПЫТ
УЗБЕКИСТАНА И ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ АДАПТАЦИИ ЗАРУБЕЖНОЙ
ПРАКТИКИ**

Рустамов Зокир

Институт макроэкономических и
региональных исследований
Ведущий специалист

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируется экономическая и правовая сущность организационно-правовых форм предпринимательской деятельности. В частности, рассмотрены особенности организационно-правовых форм, применяемых на практике в

Республике Узбекистан, таких как индивидуальное предпринимательство, частное предприятие, общество с ограниченной ответственностью и акционерные общества. Наряду с этим был проанализирован опыт США, Германии, Сингапура и Южной Кореи в этой области и оценены возможности адаптации некоторых их механизмов к национальной экономике. Анализ показывает, что правильный выбор организационно-правовой формы субъектов предпринимательства играет важную роль в привлечении инвестиций, обеспечении финансовой стабильности и повышении эффективности бизнес-деятельности. На этой основе разработан ряд практических предложений для условий Узбекистана.

Ключевые слова: *предпринимательство, организационно-правовая форма, общество с ограниченной ответственностью, частное предприятие, акционерное общество, зарубежный опыт, бизнес-среда.*

Introduction.

The role of the private sector in the global economy is increasing. The country's economic growth, employment, and improvement of the investment climate largely depend on the development of entrepreneurial activity. From this perspective, the formation of effective organizational and legal mechanisms for organizing the activities of business entities is of great importance.

In recent years, Uzbekistan has been implementing large-scale reforms aimed at supporting entrepreneurship, simplifying business registration procedures, and ensuring the inviolability of private property. The state has also created institutional mechanisms to protect the rights of business entities.

At the same time, in practice, the issue of which organizational and legal form to choose for entrepreneurial activity is still relevant. This is because various forms differ in terms of financial responsibility, tax burden, investment attractiveness, and management systems.

Literature review.

Numerous scientific studies have been conducted by foreign and domestic scholars on the study of organizational and legal forms of entrepreneurial activity. One of the domestic researchers, B. Ibratov, analyzed the theoretical and legal foundations of entrepreneurial law and highlighted the legal status of business entities and their place in market relations. In his research, special attention is paid to the legal regulation of business entities.

Sufiev's research examines the legal foundations of organizing entrepreneurial relations and the formation of legal culture. The author emphasizes the importance of improving legal mechanisms in the development of the business environment.¹

Foreign researchers Yun Suk Baik, Seung Hyun Lee, and Chun Wu Lee analyzed the factors in choosing the form of ownership for business entities. According to the results of the study, although the form of individual entrepreneurship is widespread in developing countries, the need to transition to corporate forms increases as business expands.²

Also, in the experience of Singapore and the USA, limited liability companies are recognized as a convenient organizational form for small and medium-sized businesses. These models are distinguished by the simplicity of doing business and the breadth of opportunities for attracting investment.

An analysis of the research shows that existing scientific works are mainly aimed at studying the general characteristics of organizational and legal forms, and the mechanisms for adapting foreign experience in the conditions of Uzbekistan have not been sufficiently covered.

Analysis and results. The organizational and legal form of entrepreneurial activity is an important institution that determines the legal status of an economic entity, its property relations, management system, level of responsibility, and economic relations with the state. In the modern economy, this form is regarded not only as a legal category but also as an institutional factor influencing business development.

According to the theory of institutional economics, the efficiency of entrepreneurial activity depends not only on the volume of resources but also on the quality of institutions. In this regard, economist Douglass North views institutions as the "rules of the game" for economic activity. In his opinion, the more clearly and effectively legal mechanisms are formed, the more stable the actions of economic entities will be. From this perspective, the choice of the organizational and legal form of entrepreneurship is also an important element of the institutional environment. Business entities in the Republic of Uzbekistan are regulated by civil legislation, the Law "On Guarantees of the Freedom of Entrepreneurial Activity", "On the approval of the list of activities that individual entrepreneurs are allowed to engage in", and

¹ Сўфиев А. ТАДБИРКОР ШАХС ХУКУҚИЙ МАДАНИЯТИНИНГ ТАШКИЛИЙ-МЕЎРИЙ АСОСЛАРИ // Теория и практика современной науки. 2022. №4 (82).

² Baik, Y. S., Lee, S. H., & Lee, C. (2015). Entrepreneurial firms' choice of ownership forms. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 11(3), 453-471.

other regulatory documents.³. In practice, business entities may operate with or without the formation of a legal entity.

Currently, the following main organizational and legal forms are widespread in Uzbekistan:

- individual entrepreneurship;
- private enterprise;
- family enterprise;
- limited liability company;
- joint-stock company;
- joint ventures.

These forms differ from each other in their economic characteristics. The main criteria for choosing the form of organization are the volume of capital, the level of financial risk, opportunities to attract investors, the tax burden, management complexity, and the level of property liability.

The form of individual entrepreneurship is more characteristic of small business entities, and its main advantage is the simplicity of the organizational process. This form does not require significant initial capital, and the reporting system is relatively simple. However, an important disadvantage of this form is that the entrepreneur's personal property can be held liable for business obligations.

A limited liability company (LLC) is one of the most common legal forms in our country. The participants of the LLC are liable within the limits of their shares, which partially reduces financial risks. Furthermore, this form has the potential to attract investment, increase the number of participants, and expand the business.

Joint-stock companies are more common in large sectors of the economy. Their important advantage is the possibility of attracting additional capital through the issuance of securities. However, the corporate governance system in joint-stock companies is complex, and the requirements for reporting and information disclosure are high.

Analysis shows that the majority of small and medium-sized businesses in Uzbekistan operate in the form of limited liability companies. This situation is explained by the relative flexibility of this form and its ability to limit financial risks.

An analysis of the practice of foreign countries allows for important conclusions to be drawn in this field. In US practice, the Limited Liability Company (LLC) model is widely used.

³ https://gov.uz/oz/pages/Tadbirkorlik_subyektlarini_davlat_royxatidan_otkazish

Its main feature is the legal independence of the company and the limited liability of the owners. This form also has the ability to optimize tax payments.

Germany is one of the main drivers of the European economy, and small and medium-sized enterprises (Mittelstand) play an important role in the country's economy. Their share is approximately 99% of the country's enterprises. In the German economic model, these entities are the main sources of exports, innovation, and employment.

Business entities in Germany primarily operate in the following forms:

- Einzelunternehmen (individual entrepreneur);
- GmbH (limited liability company);
- UG (mini-LLC);
- AG (joint-stock company).

The UG model is considered an important innovative legal solution in Germany. A minimum capital of €25,000 is required to establish a traditional GmbH, but it is possible to establish a company with even €1 for a UG. Subsequently, a certain portion of the company's profit is accumulated and transitioned to the requirements of the GmbH.

The main goal of this mechanism is to reduce the costs of entering the market for startups and small businesses.

Singapore is considered one of the most favorable countries in the world for doing business. A digitalized system for business entities has been fully established in the country, and the following forms exist:

- Sole Proprietorship;
- Limited Liability Partnership;
- Private Limited Company (Pte Ltd).

The process of state registration of companies in Singapore is carried out through the ACRA electronic platform. All business entities will be registered in electronic form.

The Pte Ltd form is the most common model in the country. Its main features are:

- the company is an independent legal entity;
- shareholders are liable only within the limits of their shares;
- high potential for attracting investors;
- access to the international market is simplified.

Significant work on digitalization has been carried out in Uzbekistan in recent years. However, in the current system, tax, banking, licensing, and reporting services for business entities are provided through various platforms.

Comparative analysis of business entities in Uzbekistan and foreign countries

Indicators	Uzbekistan	USA	Germany	Singapore	South Korea
Main forms of business entities	Sole Proprietorship, Private Enterprise, LLC, JSC	LLC, Corporation, Sole Proprietorship	GmbH, UG, AG	Pte Ltd, LLP	Startup Corporation, SME
Business registration process	Simplified, online services available	Fully digitalized and fast	Legally strict but transparent	Fully digitalized and integrated	Digitalized through government platforms
Minimum capital requirements	Relatively flexible	Not required in some states	UG can be established with €1	Low minimum capital	Preferential conditions for startups
Level of government involvement	Moderate	Private sector dominates	Strong institutional regulation	High state-business integration	High government support
Startup support mechanisms	Partial grants and incentives	Venture capital and private investors	Innovation funds	Government grants and digital programs	Grants, loans, guarantees, incubators
Venture capital system	Developing stage	Highly developed	Moderate	Highly developed	Highly developed
Government-backed loans	Limited	Rare	Available in selected programs	Partially available	Widely implemented
Business incubator activities	Developing	Mainly private sector-based	University-based incubators	Government-supported	Public-private partnership model
Level of digitalization	Medium-high	High	High	Very high	Very high
Export promotion mechanisms	Limited support	Market-driven	Supported by banks and state programs	Government export programs	State agency support
Innovation ecosystem	Developing	Global leader	Stable innovation environment	Technology-oriented ecosystem	Strong startup ecosystem
Applicable practices for Uzbekistan	—	Venture capital and LLC model	UG phased-capital system	Unified digital platform	Step-by-step startup support system

Areas where Uzbekistan lags behind	—	Private investment environment	Innovation capitalization	Full digital integration	Government guarantees and tech ecosystem
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The comparative analysis demonstrates that in developed economies, entrepreneurial support systems extend far beyond the simple registration of business entities. In the United States, entrepreneurial development is primarily driven by private investment mechanisms and venture capital markets. Germany focuses on reducing market entry barriers through phased capitalization models such as the UG system. Singapore has established a highly integrated digital business environment where most public services for entrepreneurs are centralized within a unified electronic platform. Meanwhile, South Korea has developed a comprehensive state-supported startup ecosystem based on grants, guarantees, innovation centers, and institutional financing mechanisms.

Although Uzbekistan has implemented significant reforms aimed at simplifying business registration procedures and improving tax administration, the country still faces institutional challenges in areas such as venture capital development, innovation financing, startup incubation systems, and long-term entrepreneurial support mechanisms. Therefore, adapting selected foreign practices to Uzbekistan's national economic conditions could significantly enhance the competitiveness and sustainability of entrepreneurial entities.

One of the most common forms of business entities in the USA is a Limited Liability Company (LLC). This form is especially convenient for small and medium-sized businesses and startups, and its main advantage is the protection of the entrepreneur's personal property from business debts and obligations. In the LLC model, the management system is relatively simple, and company participants have the opportunity to independently determine the internal structure. At the same time, this form allows for a twofold reduction in the tax burden through the "pass-through taxation" mechanism.⁴

The venture capital system plays an important role in the development of innovative entrepreneurship in the US economy. According to OECD data, the USA is the world's largest venture capital market and is characterized by high participation of institutional investors.⁵ Also, in the first half of 2025, the volume of attracted investments in US startups reached \$162.8

⁴ <https://stripe.com/resources/more/should-you-form-an-llc-or-a-corporation-for-your-startup>

⁵ https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/benchmarking-government-support-for-venture-capital_82cd3fe1-en/united-states_444b0f19-en.html

billion, which was mainly due to the growth of investments in artificial intelligence and high-tech companies.⁶

However, an important aspect of the US experience is that not all startups are funded through venture capital. According to a study by NORC at the University of Chicago, approximately 63% of startup funds are formed through private savings and credit cards, while the share of venture capital is relatively small. This situation indicates a high level of private initiative and independent financial responsibility in the US business environment.

In South Korea, the development of business entities is carried out through direct institutional support from the state. Special institutions such as KOSME (Korea SMEs and Startups Agency), KIBO (Korea Technology Finance Corporation), and KISED operate in the country. These organizations provide startups with loans, state guarantees, grants, mentoring, and export services.⁷

A key feature of South Korea is the phased business support mechanism. For example, in 2025, KIBO launched a special guarantee program worth 180 billion won for companies in the field of artificial intelligence, in which the credit guarantee was increased to 95% and financial payments were reduced.⁸ KISED and KOSME also provide marketing, international networking, and export services to startups. Some programs provide up to 3 billion won in government guarantees and up to 10 billion won in political funding for startups.

In the context of Uzbekistan, the experience of the United States can be used to develop the venture capital market, create flexible legal forms for startups, and stimulate private investment. Based on the experience of South Korea, it is advisable to introduce mechanisms for providing loans and phased support to state-owned business incubators and innovative startups under state guarantees. These mechanisms can serve the sustainable development of innovative business entities in Uzbekistan.

Conclusions and suggestions. The research results indicate that the organizational and legal forms of entrepreneurial activity are considered one of the important institutional factors in the development of the country's economy. The legal status of business entities, their financial accountability, investment attractiveness, and the level of state support directly influence economic activity and the competitiveness of the business environment.

⁶ <https://www.reuters.com/business/us-ai-startups-see-funding-surge-while-more-vc-funds-struggle-raise-data-shows-2025-07-15>

⁷ <https://www.mss.go.kr/site/eng/contents/view.do?menuCd=20104000000002019110651>

⁸ <https://www.kised.or.kr/menu.es?mid=a20204090000>

Analysis has shown that in developed countries, the creation of business entities is not considered merely a legal process. On the contrary, all stages—from business creation to its innovative development, financing, and entry into foreign markets—are systematically supported by state and private institutions.

In the US experience, it was observed that the financial risks of entrepreneurs were reduced through the “Limited Liability Company (LLC)” model, and an innovative business environment was formed through private investment and the venture capital market. In South Korea, it was found that the mechanism for developing startups through state guarantees, grants, innovation centers, and a system of phased financial support is highly effective. The practice of phased application of minimum capital requirements for new business entities in Germany is serving to reduce market entry barriers. In Singapore, digitalized public services and a unified electronic platform ensure a highly efficient business environment.

Although large-scale reforms have been implemented in the field of entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan in recent years, the research results showed that some institutional problems still persist. In particular, there is an insufficient special legal regime for innovative startups, an underdeveloped venture capital market, limited coverage of business incubators, and incomplete formation of long-term support mechanisms for business entities.

- In this regard, it is advisable for Uzbekistan to adapt foreign experience in the following areas:
 - introduction of simplified organizational and legal forms for innovative startups;
 - expanding the system of financing startups based on state guarantees;
 - institutional development of the venture investment market;
 - formation of a unified digital business platform;
 - expanding the network of business incubators and technology centers by region;
 - comprehensive state support for export-oriented small businesses.

In general, improving the organizational and legal forms of business entities and adapting international experience to the characteristics of the national economy can serve as one of the important factors in increasing the competitiveness of the private sector, developing an innovative economy, and ensuring sustainable economic growth in Uzbekistan.

List of references:

1. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг “Тадбиркорлик фаолияти эркинлигининг кафолатлари тўғрисида”ги Қонуни. – Тошкент, 2012.

2. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг “Масъулияти чекланган ҳамда кўшимча масъулиятли жамиятлар тўғрисида”ги Қонуни. – Тошкент, 2001.
3. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг тадбиркорлик субъектларини қўллаб-қувватлашга оид фармон ва қарорлари // [Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти расмий веб-сайти](#)
4. Ибратов Б. Тадбиркорлик ҳуқуқи. – Т.: Молия, 2001. – 256 б.
5. Сўфиев А. Тадбиркор шахс ҳуқуқий маданиятининг ташкилий-меъёрий асослари // Теория и практика современной науки. – 2022. – №4. – Б. 115–120.
6. Норт Д. Институтлар, институционал ўзгаришлар ва иқтисодиёт фаолияти. – Москва: Фонд экономической книги, 1997. – 180 б.
7. Baik Y.S., Lee S.H., Lee C. Entrepreneurial Firms’ Choice of Ownership Forms // International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal. – 2015. – Vol.11, №3. – P. 453–471.
8. OECD. Benchmarking Government Support for Venture Capital: United States. – Paris: OECD Publishing, 2024. // [OECD расмий сайти](#)
9. Korea SMEs and Startups Agency (KOSME). SME Support Programs in Korea. // [KOSME расмий сайти](#)
10. Korea Technology Finance Corporation (KIBO). Technology Guarantee Programs for Startups. // [KIBO расмий сайти](#)
11. Ministry of SMEs and Startups of Korea. Startup Support Policy and Innovation Ecosystem. // [Korea MSS Official Website](#)
12. Singapore Accounting and Corporate Regulatory Authority (ACRA). Business Registration System in Singapore. // [ACRA Official Website](#)
13. Acclime Singapore. Private Limited Company Formation in Singapore. // [Acclime Singapore](#)
14. Firma.de. GmbH and UG Capital Requirements in Germany. // [Firma.de](#)
15. Reuters. Germany to Invest €12 Billion into Startup Ecosystem by 2030. – 2024. // [Reuters](#)
16. Reuters. U.S. AI Startups Funding Surge in 2025. – 2025. // [Reuters](#)
17. NORC at the University of Chicago. Startup Capital and Entrepreneurial Finance Report. – 2024. // [NORC Official Website](#)
18. Stripe Atlas. LLC or Corporation for Startups: Comparative Analysis. // [Stripe Atlas](#)